

Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium (II) with Mepazine Hydrochloride

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Mepazine hydrochloride forms a pink coloured complex instantaneously with palladium(II) at a pH value of 0.5–4.0. The complex exhibits absorption maximum at 510–520 nm. The molar absorptivity is $4.46 \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the sensitivity of the reaction is $0.023 \mu\text{g/cm}^2$. The results of Job's method of continuous variation and molar ratio method indicate 1:1 composition for the complex which obeys Beer's law upto 12.0 ppm of palladium.

THE authors in the course of their comprehensive programme of study on phenothiazines, reported the use of phenothiazine¹ and chlorpromazine hydrochloride² as new reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium (II). The present work describes mepazine hydrochloride (MH), 10-[(1-methyl-3-piperidyl) methyl] phenothiazine hydrochloride as a sensitive reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium. A survey of chemical literature has shown that no attempt has been made to use MH as analytical reagent.

MH forms a pink coloured complex with palladium. The coloured reaction has been investigated and used for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium.

Experimental

Apparatus: Beckman Model DB Spectrophotometer with matched 1 cm silica cells was used for the absorbance measurements. A pH meter Model L1-10, from Electronic and Industrial Instruments, Hyderabad, with glass and calomel electrodes was used for measuring the pH of the solutions.

Reagents

Standard palladium (II) solution: A stock solution of palladium was prepared by dissolving palladium (II) chloride (M/s Johnson Matthey Chemicals Ltd., London) in dilute Analar hydrochloric acid and diluted to 1 litre to give 0.1 M with respect to hydrochloric acid. The solution was standardized gravimetrically by the dimethyl glyoximate method. It was further diluted to give a standard solution of 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Mepazine hydrochloride solution: A 0.2% solution of MH (M/s Warner-Lambert Research Institute, New Jersey, USA) was prepared in double distilled water and stored in a refrigerator. The stock solution was stable for 2 months.

All other chemicals and reagents used in this investigation were of analytical reagent quality.

Recommended procedure for spectrophotometric determinations: Transfer an aliquot of the stock solution containing up to 300 μg of palladium to a 25 ml volumetric flask. Add 5 ml of 1 M hydrochloric acid-1 M sodium acetate buffer (pH 2.65), 3 ml of 0.2% MH solution and dilute to the mark with double distilled water. Mix the solution well and measure the absorbance at 515 nm against a reagent blank prepared identically without palladium. The amount of palladium in the sample solution was then deduced from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary investigations have shown that addition of aqueous solution of MH to the solution of palladium (II) chloride results in the instantaneous formation of a pink coloured complex at room temperature. It has been found that in the absence of buffer the absorbance readings varied with time. The addition of 1 M hydrochloric acid to 1 M sodium acetate buffer has stabilized the complex formation. Therefore all subsequent studies were performed in the presence of hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate buffer.

Effect of pH and time: The effective pH range for the pink complex is 0.5–4.0 as shown by the constancy of λ_{max} and absorbance readings within this pH range. Below pH 0.5, the maximum intensity of the colour is not attained and above pH 4.2, a red coloured product is observed which does not obey Beer's law and does not have stoichiometric composition. Constant absorbance values are obtained immediately after adding the reagent to palladium solution in the presence of hydrochloric acid-sodium acetate buffer and remained constant for 6 hr.

Spectral characteristics of the palladium-MH complex: The absorption spectra of the pink coloured palladium-MH complex and the reagent alone are shown in Fig. 1. The pink complex exhibits absorption maximum at 510–520 nm. The absorption spectrum of the reagent alone under similar conditions shows that the reagent does not absorb at this wavelength. A

wavelength of 515 nm was used in subsequent investigations.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of reagent blank and Palladium-MH complex. 1. Reagent blank; 2. Palladium-MH complex (Pd = 5 μ g/ml).

Effect of varying reagent concentration: It is found that the maximum colour formation is attained when the mixture contains a 10-fold concentration of the reagent with the metal ion solution. The optimum amount of the reagent for spectrophotometric determination of palladium was 3 ml of a 0.2% reagent solution in a final volume of 25 ml.

Effect of order of addition of reagents and temperature: It is found that there is no change in the absorbance or in colour intensity of the complex if the order of addition of reactants are changed. The absorbance is independent of temperature over the range 4° – 97°.

Adherence to Beer's law and optimum concentration: Beer's law is valid upto 12.0 ppm of palladium. The optimum concentration range for the effective photometric determination of palladium as evaluated by Ringbom's method^{3,4} is 1.0 – 11.0 ppm.

Sensitivity and molar absorptivity of the complex: For $\log I_0/I = 0.001$, the sensitivity, as calculated from Beer's law data is 0.023 μ g/cm³ and the molar absorptivity is 4.6×10^4 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The sensitivity of MH is more than that of all the phenothiazine derivatives so far investigated except the parent compound phenothiazine.

Precision and accuracy: The precision and accuracy of the method have been studied by analysing solutions containing known amounts of palladium. The relative errors and standard deviations are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PRECISION AND ACCURACY

Palladium (II) taken, ppm	Palladium found, ppm	Relative error	Standard deviation, ppm	Range ppm
2.20	2.18	-0.91	0.027	0.074
6.40	6.40	0.00	0.012	0.202
9.58	9.60	+0.21	0.025	0.310

Effect of diverse ions: In order to assess possible analytical applications of the reaction, the effects of anions and cations which often accompany palladium have been studied. Varying amounts of the diverse ions are taken with a known amount of palladium and the colour is developed as outlined under the recommended procedure. An error of 2% in the absorbance reading was considered tolerable. The results are listed in Table 2. EDTA, thiosulphate, silver (I) and gold (III) interfere even in small amounts. Alkali and alkaline earth metal ions cause no interference. Efforts to increase the toleration limit of cations by the addition of masking agents were unsuccessful.

TABLE 2—TOLERANCE LIMIT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM (II)

Anion added	Tolerance limit for 5 μ g Pd/ml, ppm	Cation added	Tolerance limit for 5 μ g Pd/ml, ppm
F ⁻	910	Pt ⁴⁺	2
Cl ⁻	2750	Ru ³⁺	1.6
Br ⁻	865	Os ³⁺	20
I ⁻	5	Rh ³⁺	12
NO ₃ ⁻	6290	Ir ³⁺	6
SO ₄ ²⁻	9600	Fe ³⁺	2
PO ₄ ³⁻	1110	Co ²⁺	48
CH ₃ COO ⁻	735	Ni ²⁺	1470
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	240	Cu ²⁺	1860

Composition study of the palladium-MH complex: Job's method of continuous variation^{5,6} and molar ratio method⁷ are employed to establish the composition of the complex. The determinations are made in a medium of constant ionic strength (0.1 M sodium nitrate), pH 3 \pm 0.1 and a temperature of 27° \pm 1°. A plot of the absorbance against the mole fraction of palladium is shown in Fig. 2, from which it is seen that maximum absorbance is exhibited when the metal-ligand ratio corresponds to 1:1. The mole ratio method (Fig. 3) shows that palladium and MH combine in the ratio 1:1 confirming the results obtained by Job's method. The observations at 490 nm and 530 nm also confirm the existence of only one complex.

Fig. 2. Composition of Palladium-MH complex by method of continuous variation. $pH=3.0$; Temperature $=27^\circ$; $\mu=0.1$; $\lambda=515\text{ nm}$ (Concentration: 1. $2 \times 10^{-4}M$; 2. $1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$).

Fig. 3. Composition of palladium-MH complex by molar ratio method. $pH=3.0$; Temperature $=27^\circ$; $\mu=0.1$; $\lambda=515\text{ nm}$ (Concentration: 1. $2 \times 10^{-4}M$; 2. $1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$).

Evaluation of stability constant: The apparent stability constant values of the complex have been calculated from the absorbance data by two different methods: (a) Method of Foley and Anderson⁸ modified by Dey and coworkers⁹ and (b) Molar ratio method⁷. The log K values are 5.25 ± 0.1 and 5.14 ± 0.1 by the respective methods.

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